

Proof of the Required Scenarios to Cover all the Possible Cases Related to the Real-Time Automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve Provision

Jon Martinez-Rico^{id}, Ekaitz Zulueta^{id}, Ismael Ruiz de Argandoña^{id}, Mikel Armendia^{id},
and Unai Fernandez-Gamiz^{id}

NOMENCLATURE

Indices

s	Index for segments from 1 to S
t	Index for time periods from 1 to T
Ξ	Set of all variables
Ξ^*	Set of all variables not related to the BESS
Ω	Index for the set of the studied extreme scenarios
ω^e	Index for the real scenario
ω^x	Index for a general scenario
$\omega^u \subseteq \Omega$	Index for the maximum upward scenario
$\omega^d \subseteq \Omega$	Index for the maximum downward scenario
$\omega^n \subseteq \Omega$	Index for the no RT aFRR requirement scenario

Parameters

C_s^c	Cycling cost for segment s [€]
$E_d^{b,N}$	Nominal BESS capacity at day d [MWh]
$\overline{E_d^c}, \overline{E_d^d}$	Maximum energy charge/discharge in a period [MWh]
E^{rf}	Forecasted renewable production [MWh]
$\overline{P^{r+}}, \overline{P^{r-}}$	Maximum/minimum upward aFRR band offer [MW]
$\overline{P^{r-}}, \overline{P^{r-}}$	Maximum/minimum downward aFRR band offer [MW]
R_t^{rf}	Uncertainty factor considering renewable forecast errors [p.u.]
R^{ro}	Uncertainty factor considering renewable RT oscillations [p.u.]
R_t^{+-}	Ratio between upward and downward reserve offer [-]
$\overline{SoC_d}, \overline{SoC_d}$	Maximum/minimum BESS SoC at day d [MWh]
$\overline{SoC_d^e}, \overline{SoC_d^e}$	Maximum/minimum BESS SoC at the last period at day d [MWh]
$SoC_{s,\omega^e,d}^i$	Initial BESS SoC in segment s for scenario ω^e at day d [MWh]
$SoC_{\omega,d}^i$	Initial BESS SoC for scenario ω at day d [MWh]
α_t	Upward aFRR requirement in $\{\alpha_t^e, \alpha_t^{rt}, \alpha_{t,\omega}\}$ [p.u.]
$\alpha_{t,\omega}$	Upward aFRR requirement in scenario ω [p.u.]
α_t^e	Expected upward RT aFRR requirement [p.u.]
α_t^{rt}	Real-time upward aFRR requirement [p.u.]
β_t	Downward aFRR requirement in $\{\beta_t^e, \beta_t^{rt}, \beta_{t,\omega}\}$ [p.u.]
$\beta_{t,\omega}$	Downward aFRR requirement in scenario ω [p.u.]
β_t^e	Expected downward RT aFRR requirement [p.u.]
β_t^{rt}	Real-time downward aFRR requirement [p.u.]
Δt	Time step between periods [h]
η^c, η^d	Charge/discharge efficiency [p.u.]
Π_0^b	BESS price [€]
Π_t^{dm}	Day-ahead market price forecast [€/MWh]
Π_t^{e+}	Upward aFRR energy supply market price forecast [€/MWh]
Π_t^{e-}	Downward aFRR energy supply market price forecast [€/MWh]
Π_t^{r+}	Upward aFRR band market price forecast [€/MW]
Π_t^{r-}	Downward aFRR band market price forecast [€/MW]

Variables

$e_{t,s,\omega}^c$	BESS energy charge in segment s and scenario ω [MWh]
$e_{t,\omega}^c$	BESS energy charge in scenario ω [MWh]
$e_{t,\omega}^{cur}$	Curtailed renewable energy in scenario ω [MWh]
$e_{t,\omega}^d$	BESS energy discharge in scenario ω [MWh]
$e_{t,s,\omega}^d$	BESS energy discharge in segment s and scenario ω [MWh]
e_t^{dm}	Energy bid in the day-ahead market [MWh]
p_t^{r+}	Upward aFRR band offered [MW]
p_t^{r-}	Downward aFRR band offered [MW]
$soc_{t,s,\omega}$	BESS SoC in segment s and scenario ω [MWh]
$soc_{t,\omega}$	BESS SoC in scenario ω [MWh]
$v_{t,\omega}^b$	Binary term for charge/discharge in scenario ω [-]
v_t^{r+}	Binary term for upward aFRR supply [-]
v_t^{r-}	Binary term for downward aFRR supply [-]

I. INTRODUCTION

This document analyzes the extreme scenarios required in the optimization formulation to cover all the possible cases related to the automatic frequency restoration reserve (aFRR) provision in the paper entitled ‘‘Sizing a Battery Energy Storage System for Hybrid Renewable Power Plants based on Optimal Market Participation under Different Market Scenarios’’. The extreme scenarios defined in the paper are the following:

- **Maximum upward scenario:** Here, the real-time (RT) aFRR requirement is considered as the maximum (100 %) for the upward aFRR market. Therefore, all the upward band offer has to be provided. In contrast, the downward RT aFRR requirement is null. Therefore, α_{t,ω^u} and β_{t,ω^u} are as follows:

$$\alpha_{t,\omega^u} = 1, \quad \forall t \quad (1)$$

$$\beta_{t,\omega^u} = 0, \quad \forall t \quad (2)$$

- **Maximum downward scenario:** This scenario is the opposite of the one explained above. The downward RT aFRR requirement is the maximum (therefore, the HyRPP has to reduce its scheduled production), and the upward RT aFRR requirement is considered null. Therefore, α_{t,ω^d} and β_{t,ω^d} are as follows:

$$\alpha_{t,\omega^d} = 0, \quad \forall t \quad (3)$$

$$\beta_{t,\omega^d} = 1, \quad \forall t \quad (4)$$

- **No RT aFRR requirement scenario:** This last scenario considers that both upward and downward RT aFRR requirements are zero for all the bidding hours. Therefore, α_{t,ω^n} and β_{t,ω^n} are as follows:

$$\alpha_{t,\omega^n} = 0, \quad \forall t \quad (5)$$

$$\beta_{t,\omega^n} = 0, \quad \forall t \quad (6)$$

As explained in the full paper, the optimization formulation includes the upward and downward aFRR market RT requirements to set the real operation of the HyRPP. Note that, as pointed in Section III-A of the full paper, these upward and downward aFRR requirements are bounded as follows:

$$0 \leq \alpha_t \leq 1, \quad \forall t \quad (7)$$

$$0 \leq \beta_t \leq 1, \quad \forall t \quad (8)$$

$$0 \leq \alpha_t + \beta_t \leq 1, \quad \forall t \quad (9)$$

Since these requirements are not known until real operation, there could be an infinite number of scenarios to consider in the optimization. Nevertheless, as proved in Section III of this document, besides the real scenario (which is used to calculate the real degradation and operation of the plant), only two additional extreme scenarios need to be considered in the formulations presented in Section II. The reason for this is that once these scenarios are included, there always exists a feasible solution for any other scenario not explicitly defined in the formulation. Among the extreme scenarios, depending on whether the HyRPP is technically able and aims to participate in one or both the upward and the downward aFRR markets, only two of them are needed for covering all the possible aFRR requirement cases. The extreme scenarios needed for each particular case are proved and explained in Section III.

II. OPTIMIZATION FORMULATION

The following section shows all the equations included in the optimization formulations of Section IV of the full paper. Note that the explanations related to each equation can be found in the full paper. Formulation A in Section II-A refers to the case where the HyRPP consists of renewable generation and a battery energy storage system (BESS). Formulation B in Section II-B refers to the case where the HyRPP does not include a BESS.

A. Formulation A: Renewable Production + BESS

$$\max_{\Xi} r_d^{mkt,hy} - c_d^{deg} \quad (10)$$

$$r_d^{mkt,hy} = \sum_{t=1}^T \left(e_t^{dm} \Pi_t^{dm} + p_t^{r+} (\Pi_t^{r+} + \alpha_t^e \Delta t \Pi_t^{e+}) + p_t^{r-} (\Pi_t^{r-} - \beta_t^e \Delta t \Pi_t^{e-}) \right) \quad (11)$$

$$c_d^{deg} = \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{s=1}^S \frac{C_s^c \Pi_0^b e_{t,s,\omega^e}^d}{\eta^d E_d^{b,N}} \quad (12)$$

$$0 \leq e_{t,\omega^e}^{cur} \leq E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t \quad (13)$$

$$0 \leq e_{t,\omega}^{cur} \leq E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t, \forall \omega \in \Omega \quad (14)$$

$$0 \leq e_t^{dm} \leq E_t^{rf} + \overline{E^d}, \quad \forall t \quad (15)$$

$$0 \leq e_t^{dm} \leq E_t^{rf} + \eta^d \left(\sum_s soc_{t-1,s,\omega^e} - \underline{SoC}_d \right), \quad \forall t \quad (16)$$

$$0 \leq e_t^{dm} \leq E_t^{rf} + \eta^d (soc_{t-1,\omega} - \underline{SoC}_d), \quad \forall t, \forall \omega \in \Omega \quad (17)$$

$$\overline{P}^{r+} v_t^{r+} \leq p_t^{r+} \leq \overline{P}^{r+} v_t^{r+}, \quad \forall t \quad (18)$$

$$\overline{P}^{r-} v_t^{r-} \leq p_t^{r-} \leq \overline{P}^{r-} v_t^{r-}, \quad \forall t \quad (19)$$

$$p_t^{r-} \Delta t \leq e_t^{dm}, \quad \forall t \quad (20)$$

$$p_t^{r-} \Delta t \leq R_t^{rf} R^{ro} E_t^{rf} + \overline{E^c}, \quad \forall t \quad (21)$$

$$p_t^{r-} \Delta t \leq R_t^{rf} R^{ro} E_t^{rf} + \frac{1}{\eta^c} \left(\overline{SoC}_d - \sum_s soc_{t-1,s,\omega^e} \right), \quad \forall t \quad (22)$$

$$p_t^{r-} \Delta t \leq R_t^{rf} R^{ro} E_t^{rf} + \frac{1}{\eta^c} (\overline{SoC}_d - soc_{t-1,\omega}), \quad \forall t, \forall \omega \in \Omega \quad (23)$$

$$p_t^{r+} \Delta t \leq R_t^{rf} R^{ro} E_t^{rf} + \overline{E^d} - e_t^{dm}, \quad \forall t \quad (24)$$

$$p_t^{r+} \Delta t \leq R_t^{rf} R^{ro} E_t^{rf} + \eta^d \left(\sum_s soc_{t-1,s,\omega^e} - \underline{SoC}_d \right) - e_t^{dm}, \quad \forall t \quad (25)$$

$$p_t^{r+} \Delta t \leq R_t^{rf} R^{ro} E_t^{rf} + \eta^d (soc_{t-1,\omega} - \underline{SoC}_d) - e_t^{dm}, \quad \forall t, \forall \omega \in \Omega \quad (26)$$

$$0 \leq e_{t,\omega}^c \leq \overline{E^c} v_{t,\omega}^b, \quad \forall t, \forall \omega \in \Omega \quad (27)$$

$$0 \leq e_{t,\omega}^d \leq \overline{E^d} (1 - v_{t,\omega}^b), \quad \forall t, \forall \omega \in \Omega \quad (28)$$

$$\underline{SoC}_d \leq soc_{t,\omega} \leq \overline{SoC}_d, \quad \forall t, \forall \omega \in \Omega \quad (29)$$

$$soc_{t,\omega} = soc_{t-1,\omega} + \eta^c e_{t,\omega}^c - \frac{1}{\eta^d} e_{t,\omega}^d, \quad \forall t, \forall \omega \in \Omega \quad (30)$$

$$soc_{t,\omega} = SoC_{\omega,d}^i, \quad t = 0, \forall \omega \in \Omega \quad (31)$$

$$\underline{SoC}_d^e \leq soc_{t,\omega} \leq \overline{SoC}_d^e, \quad t = T, \forall \omega \in \Omega \quad (32)$$

$$0 \leq e_{t,s,\omega^e}^c \leq \frac{E_d^{b,N}}{S}, \quad \forall t \quad (33)$$

$$0 \leq e_{t,s,\omega^e}^d \leq \frac{E_d^{b,N}}{S}, \quad \forall t \quad (34)$$

$$0 \leq \sum_s e_{t,s,\omega^e}^c \leq \overline{E^c} v_{t,\omega}^b, \quad \forall t \quad (35)$$

$$0 \leq \sum_s^S e_{t,s,\omega^e}^d \leq \overline{E^d} (1 - v_{t,\omega^e}^b), \quad \forall t \quad (36)$$

$$0 \leq soc_{t,s,\omega^e} \leq \frac{E_d^{b,N}}{S}, \quad \forall t, \forall s \quad (37)$$

$$soc_{t,s,\omega^e} = soc_{t-1,s,\omega^e} + \eta^c e_{t,s,\omega^e}^c - \frac{1}{\eta^d} e_{t,s,\omega^e}^d, \quad \forall t \quad (38)$$

$$soc_{t,s,\omega^e} = SoC_{s,\omega^e,d}^i, \quad t = 0 \quad (39)$$

$$\underline{SoC_d} \leq \sum_s^S soc_{t,s,\omega^e} \leq \overline{SoC_d}, \quad \forall t, \forall s \quad (40)$$

$$\underline{SoC_d^e} \leq \sum_s^S soc_{t,s,\omega^e} \leq \overline{SoC_d^e}, \quad t = T, \forall s \quad (41)$$

$$e_t^{dm} + \sum_s^S (e_{t,s,\omega^e}^c - e_{t,s,\omega^e}^d) + (\alpha_t^{rt} p_t^{r+} - \beta_t^{rt} p_t^{r-}) \Delta t + e_{t,\omega^e}^{cur} = E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t \quad (42)$$

$$e_t^{dm} + e_{t,\omega^u}^c - e_{t,\omega^u}^d + p_t^{r+} \Delta t + e_{t,\omega^u}^{cur} = E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t \quad (43)$$

$$e_t^{dm} + e_{t,\omega^d}^c - e_{t,\omega^d}^d - p_t^{r-} \Delta t + e_{t,\omega^d}^{cur} = E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t \quad (44)$$

$$e_t^{dm} + e_{t,\omega^n}^c - e_{t,\omega^n}^d + e_{t,\omega^n}^{cur} = E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t \quad (45)$$

$$v_{t,\omega}^b, v_t^{r+}, v_t^{r-} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall t, \forall \omega \in \Omega \quad (46)$$

$$p_t^{r+} = R_t^{+-} p_t^{r-}, \quad \forall t \quad (47)$$

B. Formulation B: Only Renewable Production

$$\max_{\Xi^*} \sum_{t=1}^T \left(e_t^{dm} \Pi_t^{dm} + p_t^{r+} (\Pi_t^{r+} + \alpha_t^e \Delta t \Pi_t^{e+}) + p_t^{r-} (\Pi_t^{r-} - \beta_t^e \Delta t \Pi_t^{e-}) \right) \quad (48)$$

$$0 \leq e_{t,\omega^e}^{cur} \leq E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t \quad (49)$$

$$0 \leq e_{t,\omega}^{cur} \leq E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t, \forall \omega \in \Omega \quad (50)$$

$$0 \leq e_t^{dm} \leq E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t \quad (51)$$

$$\underline{P}^{r+} v_t^{r+} \leq p_t^{r+} \leq \overline{P}^{r+} v_t^{r+}, \quad \forall t \quad (52)$$

$$\underline{P}^{r-} v_t^{r-} \leq p_t^{r-} \leq \overline{P}^{r-} v_t^{r-}, \quad \forall t \quad (53)$$

$$p_t^{r-} \Delta t \leq e_t^{dm}, \quad \forall t \quad (54)$$

$$p_t^{r-} \Delta t \leq R_t^{rf} R^{ro} E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t \quad (55)$$

$$p_t^{r+} \Delta t \leq R_t^{rf} R^{ro} E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm}, \quad \forall t \quad (56)$$

$$e_t^{dm} + (\alpha_t^{rt} p_t^{r+} - \beta_t^{rt} p_t^{r-}) \Delta t + e_{t,\omega^e}^{cur} = E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t \quad (57)$$

$$e_t^{dm} + p_t^{r+} \Delta t + e_{t,\omega^u}^{cur} = E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t \quad (58)$$

$$e_t^{dm} - p_t^{r-} \Delta t + e_{t,\omega^d}^{cur} = E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t \quad (59)$$

$$e_t^{dm} + e_{t,\omega^n}^{cur} = E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t \quad (60)$$

$$v_t^{r+}, v_t^{r-} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall t \quad (61)$$

$$p_t^{r+} = R_t^{+-} p_t^{r-}, \quad \forall t \quad (62)$$

III. MATHEMATICAL PROOF

This section provides the proof of the scenarios required to consider in each case for fulfilling with all the possible RT upward and downward aFRR requirements. The aim is to prove that if the defined scenarios are used, there always exists a feasible solution for any other scenario not explicitly defined in the formulation.

A. HyRPP with renewable production + BESS

This subsection presents the proofs of the extreme scenarios required for cases related to the formulation of Section II-A.

1) HyRPP (renewable production + BESS) participating in both upward and downward aFRR markets:

Let ω^x be a general scenario, with α_{t,ω^x} upward aFRR requirements and β_{t,ω^x} downward aFRR requirements for each period t inside the optimization. For this scenario, the energy balance equation will be the following:

$$e_t^{dm} + e_{t,\omega^x}^c - e_{t,\omega^x}^d + \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t - \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t + e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t \quad (63)$$

The energy bid in the day-ahead (DA) market (e_t^{dm}), the upward aFRR band offered (p_t^{r+}) and the downward aFRR band offered (p_t^{r-}) are variables with the same values for all the scenarios. Then, the forecasted renewable production (E_t^{rf}) is a parameter; therefore, its value is also the same for all the scenarios. Thus, the only variables in (63) which depend on each specific scenario are the BESS charge (e_{t,ω^x}^c), the BESS discharge (e_{t,ω^x}^d) and the curtailed renewable energy (e_{t,ω^x}^{cur}). This way, we can reformulate the previous equation as follows:

$$e_{t,\omega^x}^c - e_{t,\omega^x}^d + e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t + \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t, \quad \forall t \quad (64)$$

Since all the parameters and variables in (64) are non-negative, the minimum value for the left side term of (64) is obtained when α_{t,ω^x} is 1 and β_{t,ω^x} is zero.

$$\arg \min_{\alpha_{t,\omega^x}, \beta_{t,\omega^x}} e_{t,\omega^x}^c - e_{t,\omega^x}^d + e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = \arg \min_{\alpha_{t,\omega^x}, \beta_{t,\omega^x}} E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t + \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t = \{\alpha_{t,\omega^x} = 1, \beta_{t,\omega^x} = 0, \forall t\} \quad (65)$$

Therefore, for any scenario with α_{t,ω^x} and β_{t,ω^x} aFRR provision requirements, the minimum value for the left side term of (64) is obtained with the **Maximum upward scenario** (see its definition in Section I). Note that this left side term of (64) consists of the energy stored in the BESS during period t (charge energy subtracting discharge energy) and the renewable production curtailment. Then, the Maximum upward scenario minimizes the energy stored in the BESS and/or the curtailment. The reason for this is that this scenario provides the maximum upward aFRR to the grid (thus discharging the BESS and/or reducing the curtailment) and does not provide any downward aFRR (which would charge the BESS and/or increase the curtailment). This means that, at any other scenario for any period t , the sum of the energy stored in the BESS and the curtailment is always above or equal to this minimum value.

Regarding the maximum value of the left side term in (64), it is obtained when α_{t,ω^x} is 0 and β_{t,ω^x} is 1.

$$\arg \max_{\alpha_{t,\omega^x}, \beta_{t,\omega^x}} e_{t,\omega^x}^c - e_{t,\omega^x}^d + e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = \arg \max_{\alpha_{t,\omega^x}, \beta_{t,\omega^x}} E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t + \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t = \{\alpha_{t,\omega^x} = 0, \beta_{t,\omega^x} = 1, \forall t\} \quad (66)$$

Thus, for any scenario with α_{t,ω^x} and β_{t,ω^x} aFRR provision requirements, the maximum value for the left side term of (64) is obtained with the **Maximum downward scenario** (see its definition in Section I). Therefore, the Maximum downward scenario maximizes the energy stored in the BESS and/or the curtailment. The reason for this is that this scenario provides the maximum downward aFRR to the grid (thus charging the BESS or increasing the curtailment) and does not provide any upward aFRR (which would discharge the BESS and/or reduce the curtailment). This means that, at any other scenario for any period t , the sum of the energy stored in the BESS and the curtailment is always below or equal to this maximum value.

Based on the minimum and maximum values obtained, (64) is bounded as follows:

$$E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - p_t^{r+} \Delta t \leq E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t + \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t \leq E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} + p_t^{r-} \Delta t \quad (67)$$

$$E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - p_t^{r+} \Delta t \leq e_{t,\omega^x}^c - e_{t,\omega^x}^d + e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} \leq E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} + p_t^{r-} \Delta t \quad (68)$$

All in all, as stated in the full paper, by including the Maximum upward scenario and the Maximum downward scenario in the formulation, we ensure that there is a feasible HyRPP operation schedule for any other scenario with α_{t,ω^x} and β_{t,ω^x} aFRR requirements related to p_t^{r+} and p_t^{r-} offers, regardless it is explicitly included in the formulation or not.

2) HyRPP (renewable production + BESS) participating just in the upward aFRR market:

Let ω^x be a general scenario, with α_{t,ω^x} upward aFRR requirement for each period t inside the optimization, and not participating in the downward aFRR market. For this scenario, the energy balance equation will be the following:

$$e_t^{dm} + e_{t,\omega^x}^c - e_{t,\omega^x}^d + \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t + e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t \quad (69)$$

The energy bid in the DA market (e_t^{dm}) and the upward aFRR band offered (p_t^{r+}) are variables with the same values for all the scenarios. Then, the forecasted renewable production (E_t^{rf}) is a parameter; therefore, its value is also the same for all the scenarios. Thus, the only variables in (69) which depend on the scenario are the BESS charge (e_{t,ω^x}^c), the BESS discharge (e_{t,ω^x}^d) and the curtailed renewable energy (e_{t,ω^x}^{cur}). This way, we can reformulate the previous equation as follows:

$$e_{t,\omega^x}^c - e_{t,\omega^x}^d + e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t, \quad \forall t \quad (70)$$

Since all the parameters and variables in (70) are non-negative, the minimum value for the left side term of (70) is obtained when α_{t,ω^x} is 1.

$$\arg \min_{\alpha_{t,\omega^x}} e_{t,\omega^x}^c - e_{t,\omega^x}^d + e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = \arg \min_{\alpha_{t,\omega^x}} E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t = \{\alpha_{t,\omega^x} = 1, \forall t\} \quad (71)$$

Therefore, for any scenario with α_{t,ω^x} aFRR provision requirement, the minimum value for the left side term of (70) is obtained with the **Maximum upward scenario** (see its definition in Section I). Note that this left side term of (70) consists of the energy stored in the BESS during period t (charge energy subtracting discharge energy) and the renewable production curtailment. Then, the Maximum upward scenario minimizes the energy stored in the BESS and/or the curtailment. The reason for this is that this scenario provides the maximum upward aFRR to the grid (thus discharging the BESS and/or reducing the curtailment). This means that, at any other scenario for any period t , the sum of the energy stored in the BESS and the curtailment is always above or equal to this minimum value.

Regarding the maximum value of the left side term in (70), it is obtained when α_{t,ω^x} is 0.

$$\arg \max_{\alpha_{t,\omega^x}} e_{t,\omega^x}^c - e_{t,\omega^x}^d + e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = \arg \max_{\alpha_{t,\omega^x}} E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t = \{\alpha_{t,\omega^x} = 0, \forall t\} \quad (72)$$

Thus, for any scenario with α_{t,ω^x} aFRR provision requirement, the maximum value for the left side term of (70) is obtained with the **No RT aFRR requirement scenario** (see its definition in Section I). Therefore, the No RT aFRR requirement scenario, compared to the other possible scenarios, maximizes the energy stored in the BESS and/or the curtailment. The reason for this is that this scenario does not provide any upward aFRR (which would discharge the BESS and/or reduce the curtailment). This means that, at any other scenario for any period t , the sum of the energy stored in the BESS and the curtailment is always below or equal to this maximum value.

Based on the minimum and maximum values obtained, (70) is bounded as follows:

$$E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - p_t^{r+} \Delta t \leq E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t \leq E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} \quad (73)$$

$$E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - p_t^{r+} \Delta t \leq e_{t,\omega^x}^c - e_{t,\omega^x}^d + e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} \leq E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} \quad (74)$$

All in all, as stated in the full paper, by including the Maximum upward scenario and the No RT aFRR requirement scenario in the formulation, we ensure that there is a feasible HyRPP operation schedule for any other scenario with α_{t,ω^x} aFRR requirements related to p_t^{r+} offers, regardless it is explicitly included in the formulation or not.

3) HyRPP (renewable production + BESS) participating just in the downward aFRR market:

Let ω^x be a general scenario, with β_{t,ω^x} downward aFRR requirement for each period t inside the optimization and not participating in the upward aFRR market. For this scenario, the energy balance equation will be the following:

$$e_t^{dm} + e_{t,\omega^x}^c - e_{t,\omega^x}^d - \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t + e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t \quad (75)$$

The energy bid in the DA market (e_t^{dm}) and the downward aFRR band offered (p_t^{r-}) are variables with the same values for all the scenarios. Then, the forecasted renewable production (E_t^{rf}) is a parameter; therefore, its value is also the same for all the scenarios. Thus, the only variables in (75) which depend on the scenario are the BESS charge (e_{t,ω^x}^c), the BESS discharge (e_{t,ω^x}^d) and the curtailed renewable energy (e_{t,ω^x}^{cur}). This way, we can reformulate the previous equation as follows:

$$e_{t,\omega^x}^c - e_{t,\omega^x}^d + e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} + \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t, \quad \forall t \quad (76)$$

Since all the parameters and variables in (76) are non-negative, the minimum value for the left side term of (76) is obtained when β_{t,ω^x} is zero.

$$\arg \min_{\beta_{t,\omega^x}} e_{t,\omega^x}^c - e_{t,\omega^x}^d + e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = \arg \min_{\beta_{t,\omega^x}} E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} + \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t = \{\beta_{t,\omega^x} = 0, \forall t\} \quad (77)$$

Therefore, for any scenario with β_{t,ω^x} aFRR provision requirement, the minimum value for the left side term of (76) is obtained with the **No RT aFRR requirement scenario** (see its definition in Section I). Note that this left side term of (76) consists of the energy stored in the BESS during period t (charge energy subtracting discharge energy) and the renewable production curtailment. Then, the No RT aFRR requirement scenario, compared to the other possible scenarios, minimizes the energy stored in the BESS and/or the curtailment. The reason for this is that this scenario does not provide any downward aFRR (which would charge the BESS and/or increase the curtailment). This means that, at any other scenario for any period t , the sum of the energy stored in the BESS and the curtailment is always above or equal to this minimum value.

Regarding the maximum value of the left side term in (76), it is obtained when β_{t,ω^x} is 1.

$$\arg \max_{\beta_{t,\omega^x}} e_{t,\omega^x}^c - e_{t,\omega^x}^d + e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = \arg \max_{\beta_{t,\omega^x}} E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} + \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t = \{\beta_{t,\omega^x} = 1, \forall t\} \quad (78)$$

Thus, for any scenario with β_{t,ω^x} aFRR provision requirement, the maximum value for the left side term of (76) is obtained with the **Maximum downward scenario** (see its definition in Section I). Therefore, the Maximum downward scenario maximizes the energy stored in the BESS and/or the curtailment. The reason for this is that this scenario provides the maximum downward aFRR to the grid (thus charging the BESS or increasing the curtailment). This means that, at any other scenario for any period t , the sum of the energy stored in the BESS and the curtailment is always below or equal to this maximum value.

Based on the minimum and maximum values obtained, (76) is bounded as follows:

$$E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} \leq E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} + \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t \leq E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} + p_t^{r-} \Delta t \quad (79)$$

$$E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} \leq e_{t,\omega^x}^c - e_{t,\omega^x}^d + e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} \leq E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} + p_t^{r-} \Delta t \quad (80)$$

All in all, as stated in the full paper, by including the No RT aFRR requirement scenario and the Maximum downward scenario in the formulation, we ensure that there is a feasible HyRPP operation schedule for any other scenario with β_{t,ω^x} aFRR requirements related to p_t^{r-} offers, regardless it is explicitly included in the formulation or not.

B. HyRPP with only renewable production

This subsection presents the proofs of the extreme scenarios required for cases related to the formulation of Section II-B.

1) HyRPP (only renewable production) participating in both upward and downward aFRR markets:

Let ω^x be a general scenario, with α_{t,ω^x} upward aFRR requirements and β_{t,ω^x} downward aFRR requirements for each period t inside the optimization. For this scenario, the energy balance equation will be the following:

$$e_t^{dm} + \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t - \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t + e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t \quad (81)$$

The energy bid in the DA market (e_t^{dm}), the upward aFRR band offered (p_t^{r+}) and the downward aFRR band offered (p_t^{r-}) are variables with the same values for all the scenarios. Then, the forecasted renewable production (E_t^{rf}) is a parameter; therefore, its value is also the same for all the scenarios. Thus, the only variable in (81) which depends on the scenario is the curtailed renewable energy (e_{t,ω^x}^{cur}). This way, we can reformulate the previous equation as follows:

$$e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t + \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t, \quad \forall t \quad (82)$$

Since all the parameters and variables in (82) are non-negative, the minimum value for the left side term of (82) is obtained when α_{t,ω^x} is 1 and β_{t,ω^x} is zero.

$$\arg \min_{\alpha_{t,\omega^x}, \beta_{t,\omega^x}} e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = \arg \min_{\alpha_{t,\omega^x}, \beta_{t,\omega^x}} E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t + \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t = \{\alpha_{t,\omega^x} = 1, \beta_{t,\omega^x} = 0, \forall t\} \quad (83)$$

Therefore, for any scenario with α_{t,ω^x} and β_{t,ω^x} aFRR provision requirements, the minimum value for the left side term of (82) (i.e., the total energy curtailed during period t) is obtained with the **Maximum upward scenario** (see its definition in Section I). Then, the Maximum upward scenario minimizes the curtailment. The reason for this is that this scenario provides the maximum upward aFRR to the grid (thus reducing the curtailment) and does not provide any downward aFRR (which would increase the curtailment). This means that, at any other scenario for any period t , the curtailment is always above or equal to this minimum value.

Regarding the maximum value of the left side term in (82), it is obtained when α_{t,ω^x} is 0 and β_{t,ω^x} is 1.

$$\arg \max_{\alpha_{t,\omega^x}, \beta_{t,\omega^x}} e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = \arg \max_{\alpha_{t,\omega^x}, \beta_{t,\omega^x}} E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t + \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t = \{\alpha_{t,\omega^x} = 0, \beta_{t,\omega^x} = 1, \forall t\} \quad (84)$$

Thus, for any scenario with α_{t,ω^x} and β_{t,ω^x} aFRR provision requirements, the maximum value for the left side term of (82) (i.e., the total energy curtailed during period t) is obtained with the **Maximum downward scenario** (see its definition in Section I). Therefore, the Maximum downward scenario maximizes the curtailment. The reason for this is that this scenario provides the maximum downward aFRR to the grid (thus increasing the curtailment) and does not provide any upward aFRR (which would reduce the curtailment). This means that, at any other scenario for any period t , the curtailment is always below or equal to this maximum value.

Based on the minimum and maximum values obtained, (82) is bounded as follows:

$$E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - p_t^{r+} \Delta t \leq E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t + \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t \leq E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} + p_t^{r-} \Delta t \quad (85)$$

$$E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - p_t^{r+} \Delta t \leq e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} \leq E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} + p_t^{r-} \Delta t \quad (86)$$

All in all, as stated in the full paper, by including the Maximum upward scenario and the Maximum downward scenario in the formulation, we ensure that there is a feasible HyRPP operation schedule for any other scenario with α_{t,ω^x} and β_{t,ω^x} aFRR requirements related to p_t^{r+} and p_t^{r-} offers, regardless it is explicitly included in the formulation or not.

2) HyRPP (only renewable production) participating just in the upward aFRR market:

Let ω^x be a general scenario, with α_{t,ω^x} upward aFRR requirement for each period t inside the optimization, and not participating in the downward aFRR market. For this scenario, the energy balance equation will be the following:

$$e_t^{dm} + \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t + e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t \quad (87)$$

The energy bid in the DA market (e_t^{dm}) and the upward aFRR band offered (p_t^{r+}) are variables with the same values for all the scenarios. Then, the forecasted renewable production (E_t^{rf}) is a parameter; therefore, its value is also the same for all the scenarios. Thus, the only variable in (87) which depends on the scenario is the curtailed renewable energy (e_{t,ω^x}^{cur}). This way, we can reformulate the previous equation as follows:

$$e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t, \quad \forall t \quad (88)$$

Since all the parameters and variables in (88) are non-negative, the minimum value for the left side term of (88) is obtained when α_{t,ω^x} is 1.

$$\arg \min_{\alpha_{t,\omega^x}} e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = \arg \min_{\alpha_{t,\omega^x}} E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t = \{\alpha_{t,\omega^x} = 1, \forall t\} \quad (89)$$

Therefore, for any scenario with α_{t,ω^x} aFRR provision requirement, the minimum value for the left side term of (88) (i.e., the total energy curtailed during period t) is obtained with the **Maximum upward scenario** (see its definition in Section I). Then, the Maximum upward scenario minimizes the curtailment. The reason for this is that this scenario provides the maximum upward aFRR to the grid (thus reducing the curtailment). This means that, at any other scenario for any period t , the curtailment is always above or equal to this minimum value.

Regarding the maximum value of the left side term in (88), it is obtained when α_{t,ω^x} is 0.

$$\arg \max_{\alpha_{t,\omega^x}} e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = \arg \max_{\alpha_{t,\omega^x}} E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t = \{\alpha_{t,\omega^x} = 0, \forall t\} \quad (90)$$

Thus, for any scenario with α_{t,ω^x} aFRR provision requirement, the maximum value for the left side term of (88) (i.e., the total energy curtailed during the period t) is obtained with the **No RT aFRR requirement scenario** (see its definition in Section I). Therefore, the No RT aFRR requirement scenario, compared to the other possible scenarios, maximizes the curtailment. The reason for this is that this scenario does not provide any upward aFRR (which would reduce the curtailment). This means that, at any other scenario for any period t , the curtailment is always below or equal to this maximum value.

Based on the minimum and maximum values obtained, (88) is bounded as follows:

$$E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - p_t^{r+} \Delta t \leq E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - \alpha_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r+} \Delta t \leq E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} \quad (91)$$

$$E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} - p_t^{r+} \Delta t \leq e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} \leq E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} \quad (92)$$

All in all, as stated in the full paper, by including the Maximum upward scenario and the No RT aFRR requirement scenario in the formulation, we ensure that there is a feasible HyRPP operation schedule for any other scenario with α_{t,ω^x} aFRR requirements related to p_t^{r+} offers, regardless it is explicitly included in the formulation or not.

3) *HyRPP (only renewable production) participating just in the downward aFRR market:*

Let ω^x be a general scenario, with β_{t,ω^x} downward aFRR requirement for each period t inside the optimization and not participating in the upward aFRR market. For this scenario, the energy balance equation will be the following:

$$e_t^{dm} - \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t + e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = E_t^{rf}, \quad \forall t \quad (93)$$

The energy bid in the DA market (e_t^{dm}) and the downward aFRR band offered (p_t^{r-}) are variables with the same values for all the scenarios. Then, the forecasted renewable production (E_t^{rf}) is a parameter; therefore, its value is also the same for all the scenarios. Thus, the only variable in (93) which depends on the scenario is the curtailed renewable energy (e_{t,ω^x}^{cur}). This way, we can reformulate the previous equation as follows:

$$e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} + \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t, \quad \forall t \quad (94)$$

Since all the parameters and variables in (94) are non-negative, the minimum value for the left side term of (94) is obtained when β_{t,ω^x} is zero.

$$\arg \min_{\beta_{t,\omega^x}} e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = \arg \min_{\beta_{t,\omega^x}} E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} + \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t = \{\beta_{t,\omega^x} = 0, \forall t\} \quad (95)$$

Therefore, for any scenario with β_{t,ω^x} aFRR provision requirement, the minimum value for the left side term of (94) (i.e., the total energy curtailed during the period t) is obtained with the **No RT aFRR requirement scenario** (see its definition in Section I). Then, the No RT aFRR requirement scenario, compared to the other possible scenarios, minimizes the curtailment. The reason for this is that this scenario does not provide any downward aFRR (which would increase the curtailment). This means that, at any other scenario for any period t , the curtailment is always above or equal to this minimum value.

Regarding the maximum value of the left side term in (94), it is obtained when β_{t,ω^x} is 1.

$$\arg \max_{\beta_{t,\omega^x}} e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} = \arg \max_{\beta_{t,\omega^x}} E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} + \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t = \{\beta_{t,\omega^x} = 1, \forall t\} \quad (96)$$

Thus, for any scenario with β_{t,ω^x} aFRR provision requirement, the maximum value for the left side term of (94) (i.e., the total energy curtailed during the period t) is obtained with the **Maximum downward scenario** (see its definition in Section I). Therefore, the Maximum downward scenario maximizes the curtailment. The reason for this is that this scenario provides the maximum downward aFRR to the grid (thus increasing the curtailment). This means that, at any other scenario for any period t , the sum of the curtailment is always below or equal to this maximum value.

Based on the minimum and maximum values obtained, (94) is bounded as follows:

$$E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} \leq E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} + \beta_{t,\omega^x} p_t^{r-} \Delta t \leq E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} + p_t^{r-} \Delta t \quad (97)$$

$$E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} \leq e_{t,\omega^x}^{cur} \leq E_t^{rf} - e_t^{dm} + p_t^{r-} \Delta t \quad (98)$$

All in all, as stated in the full paper, by including the No RT aFRR requirement scenario and the Maximum downward scenario in the formulation, we ensure that there is a feasible HyRPP operation schedule for any other scenario with β_{t,ω^x} aFRR requirements related to p_t^{r-} offers, regardless it is explicitly included in the formulation or not.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This document proves the extreme scenarios required for each case defined in Section III in order to cover all the possible aFRR provision requirements.

As a summary, when the HyRPP participates in both the upward and downward aFRR markets, the required scenarios to include in the formulation are the Maximum upward scenario and the Maximum downward scenario. This applies both to the case of the HyRPP with a BESS (see Section III-A1) and to the case just with renewable production (see Section III-B1). Then, when the HyRPP participates just in the upward aFRR market, the required scenarios for the optimization are the Maximum upward scenario and the No RT aFRR requirement scenario. This applies both to the case of the HyRPP with renewable production and a BESS (see Section III-A2) and to the case just with renewable production (see Section III-B2). Finally, when the HyRPP participates just in the downward aFRR market, the required scenarios to include are the No RT aFRR requirement scenario and the Maximum downward scenario. Here also, this applies both to the case of the HyRPP with renewable generation and a BESS (see Section III-A3) and to the case of the HyRPP just with renewable production (see Section III-B3).